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Energy Efficiency in Industrial Sector

Jishan Ara Mitu . Lecturer of Environmental & Resource Economics
Dhaka School of Economics

Introduction

The efficient use of energy resources in the industrial sector of Bangladesh is an imperative issue that warrants significant attention due to its implications on economic growth, environmental sustainability, and energy security.

As Bangladesh continues to undergo rapid industrialization, the energy demand in this sector has surged, leading to an increased reliance on fossil fuels and consequently higher greenhouse gas emissions (World Bank, 2022). This reliance not only strains the country's finite energy resources but also exacerbates environmental degradation and contributes to global climate change (IEA, 2021).

In the context of Bangladesh's industrial sector, particularly the garments and textile

industries, which account for over 80% of the nation's export earnings and contribute more than 10% of its GDP, there is considerable potential for energy efficiency improvements (BGMEA, 2023).

Studies indicate that implementing energy-efficient technologies and practices could enhance the aggregate energy efficiency by 25-31% within these sectors (Rahman et al., 2020).

Such improvements can lead to substantial cost savings, reduction in energy consumption, and a significant decrease in greenhouse gas emissions, aligning with both national economic goals and international environmental commitments (UNFCCC, 2018).

Furthermore, the integration of renewable energy sources, such as rooftop solar panels,

presents a viable pathway to enhance energy efficiency and sustainability in the industrial sector.

The Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA) has demonstrated a proactive approach by committing to a 30% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030, underlining the industry's recognition of the importance of energy efficiency (BGMEA, 2023).

By prioritizing energy efficiency and adopting advanced technologies, Bangladesh can enhance its industrial competitiveness, ensure economic growth, and contribute to global efforts to combat climate change (World Economic Forum, 2023).

This study aims to identify the current state of energy use in the industrial sector, evaluate the potential for implementing energy-efficient technologies, and recommend strategies to achieve substantial energy savings and reduce environmental impacts.

Current Energy Landscape in Bangladesh

The industrial sector in Bangladesh relies on a diverse mix of energy sources to meet its growing demand for power.

Natural gas is the dominant energy source, contributing approximately 51.05% of the total energy consumed in the industrial sector.

This heavy reliance on natural gas is primarily due to its domestic availability and cost-effectiveness. Furnace oil is the second-largest energy source, accounting

for 28.15% of the total energy used. It is widely used in industries for its high energy density, despite its higher environmental impact compared to other fuels. Coal, contributing 7.86%, is mainly used in energy-intensive industries such as cement and steel.

The use of coal has been growing due to its relatively low cost and abundant supply, although it raises significant environmental concerns due to high greenhouse gas emissions.

While their current share is relatively small, there is significant potential for growth in the adoption of

Diesel accounts for 5.74% of the energy consumption in the industrial sector and is primarily used in backup generators and for transportation within industrial operations. Renewable energy sources, including solar and wind, account for around 1.02% of the energy mix.

While their current share is relatively small, there is significant potential for growth in the adoption of renewables.

Hydroelectric power also contributes 1.02%, offering a clean and sustainable energy source, although its expansion is limited by geographical and resource constraints.

Overall, the industrial sector's energy mix highlights the urgent need for diversifying energy sources, improving energy efficiency, and increasing the adoption of renewable energy to ensure sustainable industrial growth in Bangladesh (Our World in Data, n.d.; World Economic Forum, 2023; Hydrocarbon Unit, 2021; Mongabay, 2022;

IEA, n.d.).

Energy Consumption Patterns in Key Industrial Sectors

Textiles and RMG (Ready-Made Garments) The textiles and Ready-Made Garments (RMG) sector is the largest energy-consuming sector in Bangladesh and plays a vital role in the country's economic development. In 2022, the RMG sector accounted for over 84% of Bangladesh's total exports, underscoring its critical importance (Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association, 2022).

However, this sector's high energy consumption poses substantial environmental challenges. Textile dyeing mills, for example, are among the largest consumers of energy and water, significantly contributing to the carbon footprint and water pollution in the country (World Bank, 2022).

The processes involved in textile production, such as spinning, weaving, and dyeing, are energy-intensive and rely heavily on natural gas and electricity. Given the sector's dominant role and its substantial environmental impact, efforts to enhance energy efficiency and sustainability are crucial.

Initiatives such as implementing energy management systems, upgrading to energy-efficient machinery, and promoting renewable energy use are essential steps toward reducing the sector's energy consumption and environmental footprint (International Finance Corporation, 2020).

These measures not only help in

conserving energy but also improve the competitiveness of Bangladesh's textile and RMG industry in the global market, where there is increasing demand for sustainable and eco-friendly products (International Labour Organization, 2021). Thus, addressing the energy challenges in the textiles and RMG sector is vital for the sustainable development of Bangladesh.

Cement and Steel

These measures not only help in conserving energy but also improve the competitiveness of Bangladesh's textile

The cement and steel industries in Bangladesh are known for their high energy intensity, making them significant contributors to the country's industrial energy consumption. Cement production, in particular, is one of the most energy-intensive processes, accounting for nearly 15% of the total industrial energy use.

This is due to the high temperatures required for the calcination process and the energy needed to grind raw materials into a fine powder. Similarly, steel production is also energy-intensive, involving processes such as melting, refining, and casting, which require substantial amounts of energy (World Bank, 2022).

Pharmaceuticals and Chemicals

The pharmaceuticals and chemicals sectors in Bangladesh are experiencing a rising demand for energy due to their rapid growth. The pharmaceutical sector, in particular, has seen substantial growth, with Bangladesh meeting nearly 98% of its domestic demand for pharmaceutical

products and exporting to approximately 150 countries. This growth has led to increased energy consumption, making energy efficiency measures essential for sustainable development. The chemicals sector also requires significant energy for various processes, including the production of raw materials and finished products.

Other Sectors

The shipbuilding, electronics, and agribusiness sectors in Bangladesh are all significant energy consumers, each with distinct energy requirements. The shipbuilding industry relies heavily on energy for processes such as steel cutting, welding, and painting, utilizing considerable amounts of electricity and fossil fuels (Islam, 2020).

The electronics industry also consumes substantial energy, primarily in the form of electricity, to power manufacturing, assembly, and testing processes, with companies increasingly adopting energy-efficient technologies like energy audits and rooftop solar panels (Sustainable and Renewable Energy Development Authority, 2022).

In the agribusiness sector, energy is used for irrigation, mechanized farming, and processing, with a growing adoption of energy-efficient practices such as alternative wetting and drying (AWD) for irrigation and agrivoltaics to optimize land use and energy efficiency (Bangladesh Investment Development Authority, 2023).

These sectors are crucial for the country's economic development, and improving energy efficiency within them is essential for sustainable growth.

Opportunities for Energy Efficiency

Energy efficiency is defined as using less energy to provide the same product or service, such as lighting, heating and transportation. Together with the move to renewable energy sources, increasing energy efficiency is considered to be one of the twin pillars of sustainable energy policy.

Energy efficiency is key to ensuring a safe and reliable reduction in energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. The International Energy Agency (IEA) has stated that improved energy efficiency in industrial processes, transportation, and buildings could lead to a 30% reduction in the world's energy needs by 2050 and help control global emissions of greenhouse gases (The HUMAN JOURNEY).

Bangladesh's socio-economic development is hindered by inconsistent electricity supply due to gas. (ed natural gas reserves essential for power generation. The unregulated gas usage and scarcity of new gas fields raise concerns for future electricity production.

Rising global coal and oil prices have prompted the government to pursue renewable energy sources, implementing load-shedding and market closures at night to conserve gas.

Renewable energy projects in progress are expected to meet slightly over 10% of total demand by 2030, which may fall short due to declining gas supply. Given the country's geographic suitability, expanding solar, wind, hydro, and biogas energy is essential. The government has introduced subsidies and favorable financing to boost renewable energy projects, but large-scale adoption requires addressing infrastructure barriers

Energy Efficiency Measures and Energy Consumption

Options	Energy Consumption in 2015 (MTOE)	Energy Efficiency Measures
Lights	0.875	LED and CFL lights
Fans	1.305	Efficient Fans
Cogenerations	2.933	Waste Heat Boiler; Absorption Chiller
Chillers	0.4	Efficient Chillers of COP greater than 5
RMG	0.770	Servo motors; Automation of aeration system; Heat recovery
Textile Dying	0.155	Cleaner Production
Steel Melting Furnance	0.614	Arc Furnance
Steel Rerolling Mill	0.1	Burner + Air Control + Insulation + Waste heat recovery

Source: World Bank

Cold Storage/ Ice Plants	0.063	High COP chiller + Insulation
Fertilizer (Urea)	1.268	New Plants
Textile Weaving	0.690	Air Jet Looms
Refrigerator	1.042	Efficient Refrigerators
AC	0.583	AC with inverter technology
Motors	1.321	Synchronous Belt + VFD + Efficient Motors
Boilers	2.625	Air control + Insulation + Economizer
Total	15.000	

Illustration: Mahdi/Econology/

and enhancing policy support. By advancing renewable energy, Bangladesh can reduce reliance on gas, lower emissions, and establish a resilient energy sector to sustain future industrial growth. (Shah Mohazzem Hossain 2023)

Innovation in Energy-Efficient Machineries

Energy-efficient machines reduce electricity bills by using less power, especially benefiting industries with continuous or heavy-duty operations. These machines also lower maintenance costs due to reduced wear and tear and often include smart technology for predictive maintenance, preventing breakdowns and minimizing downtime. Additionally, government incentives and tax breaks further enhance savings, making energy-efficient machinery a cost-effective choice for manufacturers looking to cut expenses and boost productivity. The adoption of high-efficiency motors, compressors, energy efficient HVAC

systems etc. These sorts energy-efficient equipment not only supports sustainability efforts but also improves operational efficiency across manufacturing plants. (IndMALL Automation).

In small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the leather goods and footwear manufacturing sector in Bangladesh the adoption of an energy-efficient servo motor for stitching machines are intervened. (ipa)

The system through careful audit first identifies the areas that can be improved and then through a systematic application procedure moves forward to ultimately seeking a formal recognition such as the ISO certification. Energy and environmental audits, which are key to energy and resource efficiency improvements, need to be encouraged in every industry. SMEs do not have the financial means or the understanding to employ energy managers. A well-structured program that assists SMEs in developing a

simple Environmental Management System can go a long way in energy efficiency improvement (World Bank).

The sixteen options analyzed, the more important have been summarized above

Innovation in Automation and Smart Technologies:

Automation is essential for maximizing energy efficiency in manufacturing, as it improves production speed, reduces errors and also optimizes energy use. Automated systems can adjust energy levels in real-time, powering down machinery during idle times and reducing waste without human intervention.

Additionally, automation enables predictive maintenance by detecting issues early, preventing energy loss from malfunctioning equipment. By tracking and analyzing energy usage data, manufacturers can identify inefficiencies and optimize operations further, making automation a key tool for achieving sustainability and cost savings.

Using IoT and AI for optimized energy management. (IndMALL Automation). Bangladesh is on a transformative journey to become a “Smart Bangladesh,” leveraging technology to improve citizen welfare, governance, and sustainable economic growth.

A shift from “Digital Bangladesh” to “Smart Bangladesh,” highlighting the role of advanced technologies like IoT, AI, and

blockchain in this evolution. The challenges emphasizing the need for coordinated efforts among the government, private sector, academia, and civil society, along with comprehensive policies to govern new technologies. These insights aim to guide sustainable development, empower communities, and create a brighter future for all citizens (Tanjil Ahmed, 2023).

Waste Heat Recovery:

Industrial waste heat, the unused energy from industrial processes, can be harnessed through various waste heat recovery technologies to reduce energy consumption.

Different methods and technologies used for heat recovery in different industries like power generation, steel, food, and ceramics, assessing practices that enhance energy efficiency.

Common technologies examined include recuperators, regenerators, preheaters, heat exchangers, and economizers, along with advanced systems like heat pumps, Organic Rankine cycles, and heat recovery steam generators (HRSGs).

Emerging techniques for converting heat directly to power, such as thermoelectric and thermo-photovoltaic generation, are also notable (Hussam Jouhara (2018)).

A well-structured program that assists SMEs in developing a simple Environmental Management System can go a long way in energy efficiency improvement

Process Optimization:

In today's competitive business environment, achieving optimal efficiency is essential for long-term success, and process optimization offers organizations a way to reach that goal.

By streamlining operations, reducing redundancies, and making better use of resources, businesses can operate more smoothly and efficiently.

Additionally, process optimization involves proactive risk management, identifying potential issues before they disrupt operations and enhancing the organization's resilience.

It also targets cost-saving opportunities without compromising quality, making businesses more cost-effective.

With a focus on continuous improvement, process optimization fosters better outcomes and more sustainable results. It enables organizations to maximize productivity, achieving more with the same or fewer resources.

Furthermore, it enhances time management by reducing delays, speeding up project timelines, and ensuring on-time delivery, which collectively allows the organization to perform at its highest potential.

While process automation, such as low-code solutions or ERP systems, is often seen as key to operational excellence, not all processes are suitable for automation. Applying automation to inefficient processes can worsen issues, so businesses

must analyze and optimize processes before implementing automation for the best results. Streamlining manufacturing processes to minimize energy wastage.

Renewable Energy Integration:

Renewable energy accounts for around 22% of global power generation, but this share is expected to double in the next 15 years, partly due to the rapid growth of variable renewable energy from solar photovoltaics and wind. There are several technology options available that can help integrate variable renewable energy into power systems.

Furthermore, new advances in wind and solar technologies allow them to be used over a wider range of conditions.

In the longer run, however, power systems with high shares of variable renewable power generation will require a re-thinking the traditional designs, operations, and planning practices from a technical and an economical point of view.

More than half of the total global renewable energy consumption today is based on biomass. Biomass is commonly co-fired with coal in large power plants and used in combined heat and power (CHP) plants at smaller scales.

It serves as a source of heating, hot water, and industrial process heat in sectors like chemicals, cement, pulp and paper, and food processing. (International Renewable Energy Agency).

Renewable energy accounts for around 22% of global power generation, but this share is expected to double in the next 15 years,

Bangladesh's development progress is driving a need for sustainable power generation, with a focus on renewable energy to secure long-term energy and environmental sustainability.

The country currently relies heavily on natural gas, though reserves are depleting, and future plans include coal and oil, which are less sustainable.

Bangladesh aims to increase its renewable energy share as part of the UN's Sustainable Development Goal 7 (SDG 7) and the Paris Agreement's target to limit global warming below 2°C.

While the goal to reach 10% renewable energy by 2020 (about 2000 MW) has fallen short, with only 2.85% achieved, the government is pursuing initiatives to gradually expand renewable energy use despite recent challenges. (Lway Faisal Abdulrazak et.al. 2021)

Barriers to Energy Efficiency

Financial Constraints:

Bangladesh's renewable energy sector holds significant potential but currently comprises only about 1% of the energy mix, limited by technological, regulatory, and policy gaps.

Financial barriers also restrict green project growth, as banks and financial institutions often lack understanding and capacity for green finance.

Bangladesh's Solar Home System program, led by IDCOL, has installed millions of solar systems through public-private partnerships, highlighting the potential for green financing.

Illustration: Mahdi/Econology/

However, this program now faces challenges due to uncoordinated grid expansion, poor financial management, and lack of policy oversight. For sustainable development, Bangladesh must build financial sector capacity, develop bond and equity markets, create a coordinated policy framework, and mainstream green finance. (Asian Development Bank, 2018)

Lack of Awareness and Technical Expertise

:

The energy management in the textile industry of Bangladesh, identifying barriers such as limited cost-effective technical measures, insufficient capital, and weak R&D.

Despite these challenges, concerns over rising energy costs, support from energy experts, and structured energy management programs are driving efforts toward efficiency. However, textile mills are unfamiliar with the concept of energy

service companies (ESCOs) and lack trained professionals, which hinders progress. Implementing energy management practices could improve energy efficiency in the sector by 3-4%. (A S M Monjurul Hasan. et.al., 2019)

Policy and Regulatory Gaps:

To enhance energy efficiency (EE) and energy security, Bangladesh must prioritize policy enforcement.

The 2018 Energy Audit Regulations (EAR), updated in 2024, outline procedures for energy audits and certifications.

The Sustainable and Renewable Energy Development Authority (SREDA) has designated 189 enterprises as high energy consumers, requiring them to conduct audits and report periodically.

However, merely collecting data through audits may not drive significant change.

Instead, establishing annual energy-saving targets for these enterprises could enforce compliance and encourage consistent improvements in efficiency.

SREDA could then review EE results and recommend corrective actions where necessary.

Additionally, the 2023 EE labelling regulations introduce minimum energy performance standards (MEPS) for appliances, enabling consumers to make energy-efficient choices, which should further support EE improvements across sectors. (Institute for Energy Economics and Financial Analysis 2024).

Future Outlook, Innovation in Energy Efficiency:

The future of Bangladesh's industrial sector will hinge on innovations in energy efficiency.

Technologies such as IoT-driven automation and smart energy management systems allow factories to monitor and control energy use in real-time, reducing waste.

For example, advanced monitoring systems in the shipbuilding and electronics industries are optimizing energy consumption, improving productivity, and contributing to the government's vision for a "Smart Bangladesh" (Tanjil Ahmed, 2023; IndMALL Automation, 2023).

These digital solutions, coupled with energy-efficient machinery, can lead to operational efficiency across various industrial processes.

Potential for Renewable Energy:

Expanding the share of renewable energy within Bangladesh's energy mix remains a key objective. Industrial facilities, particularly in the RMG sector, have demonstrated successful integration of solar power as a renewable energy source.

Additionally, solar mini-grids have been set up in off-grid areas, helping small-to medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) transition to sustainable energy (Islam, 2020; Asian Development Bank, 2018).

This shift reduces reliance on fossil fuels, strengthens energy security, and supports long-term sustainability goals for Bangladesh's industries.

The Path Forward:

To support the continued transition to efficient and renewable energy, Bangladesh's government has implemented supportive policies, including subsidies and tax incentives for companies investing in sustainable energy technologies.

The Sustainable and Renewable Energy Development Authority (SREDA) plays a crucial role by encouraging industries to adopt green practices, further supported by the Power System Master Plan (PSMP) 2016 and the Renewable Energy Policy (Government of Bangladesh, 2016; Sustainable and Renewable Energy Development Authority, 2022).

Through such policies, Bangladesh is positioned to develop a resilient industrial sector that is both environmentally conscious and economically robust.

Conclusion

The efficient use of energy resources in Bangladesh's industrial sector is essential for ensuring long-term economic growth, sustainability, and energy security. This paper highlights the complex interplay between different types of energy—natural gas, electricity, coal, oil, and renewables—and the industrial sector's productivity, operational costs, and environmental impact.

Natural gas and electricity remain the primary sources driving industrial output, but reliance on these sources brings challenges related to supply stability, pricing, and environmental concerns. Coal and oil, while cost-effective, are less sustainable, underscoring the need for cleaner alternatives.

Renewable energy, though currently a minor contributor, offers a promising path toward a resilient and sustainable energy system. Solar, biomass, and other renewable sources have the potential to reduce dependency on fossil fuels and lower greenhouse gas emissions.

However, adopting these technologies requires overcoming financial, infrastructural, and awareness-related barriers. Government incentives, regulatory reforms, and partnerships with international organizations are crucial to accelerating this transition.

Overall, achieving energy efficiency in Bangladesh's industrial sector demands a multi-faceted approach. This includes policy adjustments to encourage renewables, modernization of outdated infrastructure, and implementation of energy management systems.

With a strategic energy mix and commitment to sustainability, Bangladesh can enhance industrial productivity, reduce operational costs, and meet its sustainable development goals, thereby strengthening the foundation for a resilient industrial future.

About the Author:

Jishan Ara Mitu is an academician of Environmental and Resource Economics Programme at DScE and former research associate of CPD. Her interested areas of teaching are economics, fiscal budget, energy economics, natural resource management and environment.

She can be reached at:

jishan.mitu@dsce.edu.bd

African Energy Transition Bank

A catalyst for development or an inst of climate delayism?

Oluwaseun James Oguntuase, PhD . From Lagos, Nigeria

In response to the decreasing global investment in the oil and gas industry, the African Petroleum Producers Organization (APPO) partnered with the African Export–Import Bank (Afreximbank) to establish an institutional framework known as the African Energy Transition Bank (AETB) through a multilateral treaty. The AETB, which has an initial capital of USD 5 billion, was officially established with the signing of its founding agreement and charter on June 3, 2024, in Cairo, Egypt, and is anticipated to commence operations in the first quarter of 2025.

This institution is designed as an independent, supranational, pan-African entity dedicated to energy development, aiming to finance the advancement of all energy sources across Africa to address the existing energy poverty. Its main goal is to support African economies dependent on fossil fuels in transitioning systematically

and equitably towards low-carbon and climate-resilient economies by ensuring efficient and predictable capital distribution between fossil fuels and renewable energy sources.

The African Petroleum Producers Organization (APPO) was founded on January 27, 1987, with the purpose of promoting the use of petroleum resources to strengthen energy security, foster sustainable development, and support economic diversification across Africa.

Its mission encompasses creating a collaborative framework for African nations engaged in petroleum production, aiming to maximize the developmental and welfare benefits derived from petroleum exploitation for its member countries and the broader African continent. Since its inception, APPO's membership has expanded from eight member states in 1987

to a current total of eighteen members.

APPO does not dispute the scientific consensus on climate change or the associated risks, nor does it oppose mitigation of climate change's threats or transition to alternative energy sources. However, the organization argues that Africa should not "be forced to take the fast track of energy transition as demanded by the Western world", especially since the continent is frequently mentioned "in passing, or at best as an appendage" in global energy policy discussions.

APPO asserts "that measures and policies introduced to check climate change should not be uniformly imposed on all societies without regard to their special circumstances, like their levels of socio-economic development and energy poverty (APPO, 2023e)".

The organization emphasizes that "Africa cannot afford to abandon any form of energy.... [but]....need all the energies we can get".

Afreximbank stands as the leading Pan-African multilateral financial institution dedicated to facilitating and enhancing both intra- and extra-African trade. The institution's initiatives integrate climate change considerations with developmental objectives, advocating for a fair energy transition and fostering sustainable development by aligning climate action with its trade and development finance responsibilities.

The debate persists regarding whether the establishment of the AETB should be viewed as a developmental initiative for Africa or as a means of institutionalizing

The debate persists regarding whether the establishment of the AETB should be viewed as a developmental initiative for Africa or as a means of institutionalizing climate delayism. Delayism refers to a deliberate and organized approach aimed at fostering unwarranted fear surrounding various climate initiatives, ultimately seeking to hinder or postpone these efforts indefinitely. This approach exploits the notion that tackling the climate crisis will negatively impact daily life, thereby attempting to prolong reliance on fossil fuels for as long as possible.

Proponents of the AETB argue that Africa should leverage its significant oil and gas reserves to achieve developmental parity with the Global North and enhance its climate resilience. This argument is heavily influenced by legacy emissions debate; a common argument among African nations is that developed countries contribute more to pollution, which justifies their pursuit of energy poverty alleviation and the right to achieve similar levels of development through the use of fossil fuels.

Conversely, environmental advocates call for a complete shift away from fossil fuels, asserting that Africa should bypass traditional fossil fuel reliance by harnessing its abundant renewable energy resources as the most effective strategy for fostering development. Supporters of this perspective can highlight the stark reality that nearly half of Africa's population lacks access to electricity, with approximately 900 million individuals, or 75 percent, without any form of modern

energy. Many countries on the continent depend heavily on oil and gas revenues to fulfill governmental responsibilities, including security, healthcare, education, and essential infrastructure for socio-economic advancement. Consequently, oil revenues remain crucial for the continent's economic growth, human development, and political stability. The APPO has warned that the repercussions will not be confined to Africa. The current dangers of crossing the Mediterranean into Europe will seem trivial compared to what the world will witness if Africa is pressured to abandon its fossil fuels and is unable to access the promised renewable energy sources.

The environmental movement's camp acknowledged that energy poverty is a significant barrier to development in Africa. However, they contended that delay in addressing this issue poses a serious threat to the well-being of the African population. The continent is highly vulnerable to the adverse effects of climate change, exacerbated by the interaction of multiple stresses occurring at various levels, dependence on climate-sensitive industries, and limited capacity to adapt.

Africa is endowed with abundant renewable energy resources, and as the costs of new renewable technologies continue to decrease, they are becoming more affordable than the least expensive fossil fuels. This positions Africa to potentially achieve universal energy access while simultaneously lowering the carbon intensity of its growth and reducing carbon dioxide emissions. The concept of climate delayism—postponing climate action until Africa attains higher economic development and improved social conditions—driven by short-term economic interests or political inertia,

will incur long-term costs of inaction that far exceed any immediate advantages. As highlighted by Afreximbank, the cost of immediate and decisive action is far less than the cost of inaction and delayed efforts. The implications of delaying action are too critical to ignore.

About the Author

Oluwaseun James Oguntuase is a researcher hailing from Lagos State University who has authored several articles on issues like Sustainable Development and Entrepreneurship.

He can be reached at:

oluwaseunoguntuase@gmail.com

Communicating climate change: Turning awareness into action

Samsun Nahar

A Climate rally in Columbia University, March 15, 2019; Source: AP

Climate change is no longer a distant threat—it's the unsettling reality shaping our lives, economies, and landscapes every day. Yet, we seem to live in oblivion.

In Bangladesh, a country at the frontline of climate vulnerability, this indifference is a luxury we simply cannot afford.

Recently, videos of anglerfish and oarfish have gone viral. These bioluminescent creatures from the deepest, darkest part of the ocean, suddenly appearing near the surface.

Scientists believe climate change is disrupting ocean currents, possibly forcing them out of their habitat. It feels like nature is waving a red flag, reminding us that

the crisis isn't coming—it's already here. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change IPCC confirms that since 1850, human activities have been the primary driver of global warming, while natural events have played a negligible role.

And the pattern makes it almost inevitable that global temperature might reach or exceed 1.5°C in coming decades.

Now, our actions—or inactions—shape the future.

And, in this era of disinformation, effective climate communication can serve as the primary catalyst. Effective climate communication is not just about raising awareness; it's about inspiring action. By

maximizing strategic messaging, media outreach, and behavioral insights, we can turn passive concern into proactive change. Because in the fight against climate change, knowledge isn't just power—it's survival.

Understanding public perception of climate change

In October 2024, Bangladesh's Ministry of Environment, Forest, and Climate Change banned single-use polythene and polypropylene in supermarkets.

This policy shift ignited debates among consumers and businesses.

Many emphasized on the 'lack of a cheap alternative' or the 'inconvenience of carrying ecofriendly shopping bags'.

Such reactions underscore a broader issue: even the urban and educated segment of the population remains disconnected from the pressing realities of environmental degradation.

Ranked as the ninth most disaster-prone country for consecutive years (World Risk Report 2024), Bangladesh faces rising sea levels, extreme weather, and environmental degradation. Yet, the perception of climate change as a future rather than an immediate problem hinders necessary action.

Here we see two big misconceptions about climate change. First, it's seen as a secondary issue—less urgent than political or economic crises—when, in reality, it's

disrupting our daily lives. Second, many still think it's a distant threat, but we're already seeing its impact everywhere, from extreme weather to food shortages. Climate communicators must focus on both aspects to bridge the knowledge gap.

Closing the knowledge-action gap

A 2020 UNICEF survey revealed that approximately 85% of Bangladeshi youth learn about climate change in school, the highest rate in South Asia.

However, about half of the respondents perceived climate change as a future problem rather than an immediate concern.

This disconnect suggests that while information is disseminated, its perceived relevance remains limited.

Effective climate communication involves translating scientific data into relatable narratives, visuals, and real-life impacts, making the crisis more comprehensible and urgent.

Historically, Bangladesh has successfully utilized media to address public health crises.

In the 1990s, coordinated efforts between the government and NGOs, also boosted by Bangladesh Television's programming, significantly raised awareness about crises like overpopulation, acid violence and diarrhea. Similar strategies can be employed for climate communication, utilizing both

A 2020 UNICEF survey revealed that approximately 85% of Bangladeshi youth learn about climate change in school, the highest rate in South Asia.

traditional and digital platforms to reach diverse audiences.

Emphasis on sector-wise climate risks

Climate change affects different sectors in distinct ways, making targeted communication essential. By highlighting sector-specific threats, media can foster a deeper understanding of climate change's economic, social, and humanitarian consequences. Thus, it must ensure that policies and actions are tailored to the needs of affected industries and communities.

Agriculture: Bangladesh loses approximately \$1 billion annually to tropical cyclones (World Bank). By 2050, one-third of agricultural GDP may be lost due to climate extremes, threatening a sector that employs nearly half the population.

Migration: Climate displacement could force 13.3 million people to migrate internally by 2050, disproportionately affecting women.

Economy: Severe flooding could shrink GDP by up to 9%, highlighting economic vulnerability.

Garment Industry: Extreme heat has risen significantly in Dhaka and other key production hubs. Cornell University's Global Labor Institute found a 42% increase in dangerously high heat days from 2020 to 2024 compared to 2005–2009, threatening worker health and productivity.

Health: The WHO reports that extreme

heat kills nearly half a million people annually—more than war and terrorism combined. Climate change also intensifies outbreaks of malaria, cholera, and dengue, while wildfire pollution contributes to chronic diseases.

Harnessing media and digital platforms

Bangladesh has a vast media network, including 1,248 daily newspapers, 45 private TV channels, 4 state-run TV channels, 28 FM radio stations, and 32 community radio stations. These platforms offer a powerful means to drive climate awareness and action.

The digital landscape has also expanded rapidly, with 132.8 million internet users and a 22.3% rise in social media engagement in 2024. Facebook alone reaches 52.9 million users, making it a key tool for climate communication. (The Daily Star)

With the necessary tools and platforms to communicate climate change, all we have to do is make it matter more in the newsroom. So far only a few newspapers have shown relentless efforts to boost public awareness about climate issues through effective strategies.

Further strategies include:

Relatable messaging: Avoiding technical jargon and connecting climate issues to familiar concerns—health, family, and economic stability—improves engagement.

Visual storytelling: Using compelling imagery and real-life stories makes climate

With the necessary tools and platforms to communicate climate change, all we have to do is make it matter more in the newsroom.

threats feel immediate and personal, fostering stronger emotional connections. Driving behavioral change through strategic messaging

Climate communication should inspire action, not just inform. Key strategies include:

Highlighting feasible actions: A Dhaka resident discards an average of 22.25 kg of plastic waste annually, significantly contributing to urban pollution (World Bank, 2021). Highlighting such statistics can encourage behavioral shifts, such as reducing single-use plastics, adopting reusable alternatives, and segregating waste. When multiplied across millions, these small behavioral shifts create significant environmental benefits and drive policy change.

Showcasing positive change: Success stories motivate collective action. Bangladesh's solar home system initiative has provided clean energy to over six million rural households, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and improving livelihoods (2024). Demonstrating achievable solutions encourages widespread adoption of sustainable practices.

Combating misinformation and greenwashing

False claims and corporate greenwashing are slowing real climate action. Companies paint themselves as “green” while continuing harmful practices, and misinformation fuels doubt, making people question the urgency of the crisis. The IPCC warns that these misleading narratives create confusion, delaying the action we desperately need. The solution? Clear, honest, and science-backed communication that helps people

see through deception and understand the truth.

Communicating with optimism

Climate change is serious, but if we only talk about disaster, we risk leaving people feeling powerless. Doom and gloom alone won't inspire action—hope will. When we highlight solutions, showcase real progress, and emphasize the power of collective action, we turn despair into determination. Therefore, people need to know that change is possible, and that their actions, no matter how small, truly matter. For that we need voices that move people and drive action.

Policymakers, activists, and journalists must come together, using their platforms to cut through the noise and make climate action impossible to ignore. When leaders push for change, when stories inspire action, and when truth drowns out doubt, real progress begins. The right words, in the right voices, can change the future.

About the writer

***Samsun Nahar** is a communication professional deeply concerned about climate change. Believing in the power of media and the voices of people, she writes to turn awareness into action. Because when people wake up, change isn't just possible—it's unstoppable.*

She can be reached at:

rakhy09@gmail.com

Rethinking Sustainability: Beyond greenwashing and towards real impact

By Marla Lise . Singapore

Illustration: Mahdi/Econology/

Sustainability is everywhere. It dominates corporate reports, conference panels, and marketing campaigns. We see it in glossy advertisements, on product packaging, and in job descriptions. Yet, despite its ubiquity, environmental crises deepen, emissions continue to rise, and biodiversity plummets. It's time to ask: What is the real objective of sustainability? And are we actually making progress, or just perfecting the illusion of it?

Origins of modern sustainability

The mainstream concept of sustainability, as we know it today, was formalized in 2004 through the United Nations' Who Cares Wins report. Endorsed primarily by financial institutions, this initiative linked sustainability to economic resilience rather than planetary well-being. The report emphasized how companies could increase shareholder value by managing risks, anticipating regulation, and protecting

brand reputation. A simple word search of the document shows that 'climate' is frequently collocated with 'financial,' 'earnings,' 'competitiveness,' and 'risk.' Sustainability, at least in its corporate context, was never about saving the planet—it was about protecting profits from environmental disruptions.

The rise

The sustainability sector has exploded in recent years, offering career opportunities for those eager to drive positive change. Yet, many entering the field have little or no background in environmental science.

Professionals are often recruited from marketing, communications, or human resources teams to craft compelling narratives about corporate responsibility. Sustainability reporting has, in many cases, become an exercise in greenwashing rather than a genuine effort to reduce environmental harm.

Materiality—the principle that dictates what gets included in sustainability reports—is highly subjective. Companies have the freedom to highlight the issues that present them in the best light while downplaying inconvenient truths. Some reports stretch to 100 pages; others condense everything into a polished 12-page summary. The inconsistencies raise an unsettling question: If companies can selectively disclose their sustainability efforts, how do we hold them accountable?

Business of greenwashing

Sustainability is now a lucrative business. Recognition as a ‘sustainability leader’ can be bought through paid features in magazines or sponsorships at high-profile environmental conferences. Many speakers at these events represent companies with questionable environmental track records, yet their narratives are carefully curated to align with sustainability goals.

The reality is that corporations invest heavily in public relations to shape their green image, often without making substantive changes to their business practices.

Even widely accepted sustainability practices are riddled with contradictions. Take carbon offsetting—a strategy in which companies compensate for emissions by funding projects like tree planting. While it sounds promising, it often serves as a license to continue polluting rather than a

genuine effort to decarbonize.

The same applies to recycling initiatives. Many ‘recycled plastic’ products cannot be reliably verified, and in regions lacking recycling infrastructure, they often end up in landfills or the ocean anyway. Yet, these efforts contribute to the appearance of sustainability, providing reassurance without real accountability.

Many speakers at these events represent companies with questionable environmental track records, yet their narratives are carefully curated to align with sustainability goals.

Problem with sustainability reporting

The sheer volume of sustainability reports being produced raises another concern—how much carbon is emitted just to document sustainability efforts? Between printing, data storage, and business travel for emissions assessments, the sustainability industry itself contributes to environmental impact.

We spend millions developing frameworks, standards, and certifications, yet we rarely question whether these processes lead to actual improvements or merely add to bureaucratic complexity.

Why are companies investing so heavily in sustainability marketing but not in environmental education for their employees?

Why aren’t sustainability professionals required to have a foundational understanding of environmental science, climate change, or resource management? If the goal is to drive meaningful change, shouldn’t we be focusing on science and solutions rather than messaging?

Carbon tunnel vision

Climate change is often reduced to a myopic discussion about carbon emissions, but sustainability is much broader than that. Biodiversity loss, soil degradation, deforestation, and ocean acidification are equally critical.

Yet, corporate sustainability efforts often prioritize carbon accounting and carbon credits while ignoring the complex ecological systems that sustain life on Earth. The emphasis on metrics and a carbon tunnel vision oversimplifies what sustainability should truly mean.

Towards action

If sustainability is to be more than a corporate buzzword, it must shift from optics to action. This means moving away from performative greenwashing and toward genuine efforts that prioritize planetary health over branding:

Embedding science into sustainability roles – Prioritize hiring experts in environmental science, resource management, and climate policy rather than relying solely on communications professionals to shape their narratives.

Holding companies accountable – Independent audits, stronger regulations, and transparent reporting mechanisms can help prevent selective disclosures and misleading claims.

Funding real solutions – Instead of spending millions on sustainability conferences and PR campaigns, businesses should invest in initiatives that restore ecosystems, support conservation efforts, and develop truly circular economies.

Educating the public – Sustainability should not just be about corporate responsibility. Schools, media, and governments should actively promote environmental literacy to empower individuals to make informed choices.

Re-evaluating our consumption models – True sustainability is not about ‘greener’ consumerism but about consuming less, reusing more, and designing products with longevity and recyclability in mind.

The future

We need to move beyond the idea that sustainability is an accessory to capitalism. If we continue to treat it as a marketing tool, we will only delay necessary systemic change. The question is no longer whether sustainability can be profitable but whether profit-driven sustainability can ever be enough.

Sustainability—when done right—still holds the power to drive meaningful change. If we strip away the greenwashing, rethink our priorities, and commit to real action, we can create a future where sustainability is not just a concept but a lived reality.

The challenge is immense, but so is the opportunity. It’s time to redefine what sustainability truly means and ensure that it serves not just corporate interests but the planet and future generations as well.

About the Author

Marla Lise is a Sustainability Impact Advisory consultant at Kowabunga Pte. Ltd, Singapore.

She can be reached at:
marla.lise@yahoo.com.au

Summer power crisis looms with renewables still struggling to catch up

Julfikar Dihan (Editorial Director)

As summer approaches, the sweltering heat of Chaitra looms over Bangladesh, pushing both public life and agricultural fields to their limits.

With rising temperatures, the demand for electricity is also set to surge.

Energy Adviser Fouzul Kabir Khan on February 5 said that electricity demand is expected to reach 15,700 MW during Ramadan, and may rise further to 18,000 MW in the peak summer months when irrigation demand increases.

Despite Bangladesh Power Development Board (BPDB) data indicating a total installed capacity of 27,790 MW, the country faces persistent fuel shortages, creating a

major obstacle to stable electricity supply.

Daily load shedding could range between 700 MW and 1,400 MW during this period and to mitigate the shortfall, the government plans to import four LNG cargoes to meet the additional demand for power generation, according to the adviser.

However, while fossil fuels remain central to the country's energy strategy—relying heavily on gas, coal, and furnace oil—the role of renewable energy remains uncertain.

Ambitions and roadblocks

The deposed Awami League government set an ambitious target of generating 40% of the country's electricity from renewable

sources by 2041. However, the Sustainable and Renewable Energy Development Authority (SREDA) reports that the country's current on-grid renewable energy capacity, including solar, wind, and hydro, stands at just 1,176 MW, increasing to 1,557 MW when off-grid systems are included.

Currently, the contribution of renewables to the national grid is below 5%. A number of other issues also make the target of 40% a far cry given the current state of the power sector.

These issues include non-alignment of major plans prepared by the Ministry of Power Energy and Mineral Resources (MoPEMR) and Ministry of Environment and Climate Change (MoECC) with regard to the target, a number of non-renewable energy mixes considered 'clean energy' along with renewable energy under the plan prepared by the MoPEMR, and lack of clarity about the disaggregated amount for 40 percent to be generated from renewables, since the projected demand for electricity in 2041 is questionable, according to the Centre for Policy Dialogue (CPD).

Experts argue that Bangladesh's heavy reliance on energy imports—both fossil fuels and electricity—necessitates a stronger focus on domestic renewable energy.

Increasing renewable energy capacity would help reduce dependence on international markets, lessen import costs, and preserve foreign currency reserves.

Economic toll forecast

During 2022–2028, the government would have to spend over \$228 million for importing LNG, which would be required to meet the domestic demand, according to CPD [Khondaker Golam Moazzem and Moumita A. Mallick].

In addition, a report from the Institute for Energy Economics and Financial Analysis (IEEFA) estimates that a more ambitious clean energy capacity target of 40% by 2041 (without storage facilities) would require an annual investment of \$1.53 billion to \$1.71 billion from 2024 through to 2041.

“A more structured business model is needed as an alternative to costly diesel-based irrigation.”

Barriers to Renewables

Shafiqul Alam, Lead Energy Analyst for IEEFA Bangladesh, identified high import duties on renewable energy equipment as a key issue.

He said, “High import duties pose a major challenge for small-scale — rooftop solar, mainly the decentralised — implementation. Since we import the equipment, there is a specific import duty involved.

Although it is feasible when calculated based on the levelised cost of energy, this additional cost remains a significant obstacle.”

He mentioned that the process of getting finance for it is a bit complicated, especially the green finance fund of Bangladesh Bank is a bit difficult to access. Solar irrigation, an area with significant potential, also faces hurdles. “Solar irrigation systems operate for only 120–140 days a year. The challenge lies in making use of the infrastructure for

the rest of the year to ensure commercial viability,” explained Alam. “A more structured business model is needed as an alternative to costly diesel-based irrigation.” Land scarcity poses another problem for large-scale solar projects. He pointed out that acquiring land is highly complex due to fragmented ownership.

“To generate 100 MW of solar power, about 300 acres of land is required. However, securing this land is incredibly difficult as it often belongs to 50–100 different owners,” he noted, adding that the government could have allocated state-owned land for such projects.

A revised renewable energy policy is in the works, and there is discussion about offering tax waivers for decentralised rooftop solar systems.

Alam suggested that Bangladesh Bank should consider creating a dedicated financing scheme for renewable energy and that SREDA should actively motivate industry owners to promote adoption.

“The most practical step would be to install 1,000–2,000 MW of rooftop solar as soon as possible,” he recommended.

A window for foreign investment

Dr SM Nasif Shams, associate professor and director of the Institute of Energy at Dhaka University, as well as a board member of SREDA, highlighted growing international interest in Bangladesh’s renewables sector.

“Several foreign companies are eager to invest. Previously, there was hesitation and bias, but now we must be careful to retain this interest and ensure steady progress,” he said.

Shams stressed that political uncertainty should not deter progress. “Governments may change, but renewable energy projects need long-term commitment. Even if large-scale projects take time, smaller initiatives should continue without disruption,” he added. “Many projects initiated under the previous government are at various stages of completion and should be prioritised.”

Deepening of enmity

By Mahdi Hasan & Md. Rashedul Hasan Siam

Despite simmering tensions, the first round of the US-Iran nuclear talks was relatively peaceful, though the war feels as near as ever. The meeting took place in Muscat on 15th April through the surrogates of Tehran and Washington.

There was also an ambiguity over the possible nature of the meeting. Tehran repeatedly discarded any possibility of direct meetings after President Trump's statement on 30th April, 2025.

Washington's demands

The Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) agreement of 2015 was in jeopardy after the first Trump administration withdrew the agreement for a 'better deal'. The walkout was soon followed by a series of assassinations targeting nuclear scientists as well as military figures. This led to a cooling of relations between Tehran

*Houthi supporters holding a picture of Abd al Malik al Houthi during an anti-U.S. and anti-Israel rally in Sanaa, Yemen, March 17, 2025.
Source: AP*

and Washington as Iran responded with retaliatory attacks targeting the US interests in the Middle East.

After President Trump assumed power for the second time, he soon resumed his hostile position towards the 'Axis of Resistance', which included the relabelling of the Ansarallah of Yemen as a designated terrorist organization.

It was assumed that the US would push for complete denuclearization based on President Trump's repeated provocations and media statements.

However, on April 15th 2025, the president's envoy, Steve Witkoff, told Fox News about limiting Uranium enrichment, which was almost in par with the 2015 Nuclear deal, except that now, the US wants Iran to disclose its military capabilities.

*Steve Witkoff with President-elect Donald Trump at Mar-a-Lago, Jan. 7,
Source: Reuters*

AN OVERVIEW OF THE MAJOR NON-STATE ALLIES OF 'AXIS OF RESISTANCE'

Post October 7th

560+

days since Oct 7th 2023

Hezbollah

Ansarallah (Houthis)

Islamic Resistance Movement (Hamas)

Hashd al Sha'bi

October 8th, 2023
Beginning of Israel-Hezbollah war

October 17th, 2023
Initiation of Hezbollah's **Battle of the Mighty Ones**

Ceasefire
November 27th, 2024
Eventual withdrawal from Southern Lebanon and Israeli occupation of Lebanese territory

Atleast 75 Lebanese Civilians killed from Israeli airstrikes after the ceasefire - UN

130
Israeli Soldiers killed, 1,250 wounded

59
Merkava Tanks destroyed

16
Military vehicles Incl bulldozers, Humvees, armored vehicles

4,637
Total Operations launched by Hezbollah

100 Attacks on ships
4 seafarers killed
2 vessels sunk

101 Missiles launched Incl Ballistic, cruise, and hypersonic missiles

78 Total Operations launched by Houthis

Al Aqsa Flood begins
October 7th, 2023
Hamas attacks Israel amid normalization attempts

October 9th
Israel starts siege of Gaza

Oct 19th
Houthi involvement

Oct 27th
Israeli ground offensive begins

First Ceasefire
November 24th-December 1st, 2023

Ceasefire violated

April 13th, 2024
Iran launches 300 missiles on Israel as a retaliation

Second Ceasefire
November 24th, 2025

Ceasefire violated

\$67B

Drained from Israeli Occupational Forces by Palestinian resistance

1000+

Military vehicles neutralized by Hamas up until Jan, 2024

The Axis in disarray

President Pezeshkian's willingness to engage with the US ruffled some feathers among the hardliners. In January 2025, the government spokesperson, Fatemeh Mohajerani reiterated that the talks will happen under the direction of the SNSC (Supreme National Security Council) amidst the rising tensions within the government. Ayatollah Khomeini, meanwhile, shifted from a stance 'total rejection' of direct talks to adopting a stoic, albeit conforming,

Ayatollah Ali Khamenei speaks during a meeting with government officials in Tehran, Iran, April 15, 2025.

attitude for an indirect one. He emphasised that Iran should temper its expectations, neither overly hopeful nor unduly cynical, regarding the outcome of these discussions. Tehran's pragmatic approach towards the US begins as Iran slowly loses control over its regional non-state allies. Hezbollah, the 'Shia militia group' is facing mounting pressure from Washington to disarm itself and merge with the Lebanese military

The proposal from the Lebanese President came weeks after Hezbollah pulled out of Southern Lebanon. The group lost its leader and a huge portion of its military personnel last year as well..

In a 'solidarity meeting' held on April 15th, 2025, Sheikh Hussein Ghabris, the group's head of public relations, mentioned that the group will not accept 'normalization' or disarmament, though it is open for cooperation as a defense strategy with the Lebanese state. The member of parliament and the deputy head of Hezbollah's political

US bombing of Yemeni Ras Isa fuel Port on 17th April, 2025; Photo: Collected

council, Mahmoud Qamati had harsher words for a proposed disarmament, saying “any hand that reaches out to take them will be cut off”.

The situation is also grim for the ‘Axis’ in Iraq. Some anonymous commanders of militia groups like Kata’ib Hezbollah, Nujabaa, Kata’ib Sayyed al-Shuhada, and Ansarullah al-Awfiyaa agreed to disarmament, allegedly on receiving permission from the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps (IRGC) to avoid drastic measures from Israel and the US coalition, according to

Kata’ib Hezbollah militias marching in the streets of Baghdad for its slain commander; Source: Reuters

an interview given to Reuters. There has been no official statement from the groups confirming or rejecting such claims. Iran’s most staunch ally, the Ansarallah Houthis of Yemen, have remained vigilant despite the US bombing campaign that began in the middle of March.

The airstrikes targeted military infrastructure, fuel terminals, and civilian gatherings. The coalition plans to exhaust the Houthis to pave the path for a ground invasion by the pro-US proxies. US Defence Secretary Pete Hegseth, called it “a bad three weeks for the Houthis” and warned that “it’s only about to get worse”, emphasizing that the US will not relent despite the devastating nature of the campaign.

The US campaign began after the Houthis resumed their attacks on commercial ships by maintaining a strong grip over the naval chokepoints, as the Gaza Ceasefire failed.

A week after the UAE-backed de facto government suggested taking over Al Hudaydah port to advance towards San’aa and the rest of the ‘fifth district’, the US Central Command (CENTCOM) has bombed the Ras Isa port of the Hudaydah

region. The attack represents a blatant violation of the UN-brokered Stockholm Agreement, which explicitly bars any military action in Hudaydah due to the port city's strategic and humanitarian significance. The issue could be further convoluted due to the presence of Russian and Chinese ships in the area.

The Houthis, on the other hand, have continued firing missiles at Israeli airports and are taking down drones and aircraft, along with repeated attacks on US warships in the Red Sea.

The Economic Perspective

The decades-long tension between the US and Iran extends far beyond political rhetoric, it has cast a long shadow over economic relations, shaping trade dynamics, energy markets and regional stability.

Quick History

To understand today's US-Iran tensions, it's essential to revisit key moments in history.

In 1953, the US played a pivotal role in orchestrating a coup that ousted Iran's democratically elected Prime Minister, Mohammad Mossadegh.

The move sparked deep resentment among many Iranians. That anger simmered for decades until it boiled over in 1979, when Iran underwent a revolution that overthrew the monarchy. The newly established Islamic Republic viewed the US, famously branding it "the Great Satan".

That same year, Iranian students stormed the US Embassy in Tehran, taking 52 Americans hostage and holding them

for 444 days—a dramatic episode that cemented the deep mistrust between the two nations.

What Are Sanctions?

A major source of friction between the US and Iran lies in the use of economic sanctions. Sanctions are a tool used by governments to pressure other nations to change their behaviour, often by restricting trade or financial transactions. Over the years US has imposed economic sanctions against Iran, targeting its vital oil exports and limiting its ability to engage in global business.

Oil: The Heart of the Matter

Iran sits atop some of the world's largest oil reserves. Before US-led sanctions took place, Iran exported millions of barrels a day and earned billions of dollars in revenue. Oil money used to build infrastructure, fund healthcare and education.

However, when the sanctions were imposed, the ability to sell its oil plummeted. Some countries halted purchases altogether. The result was a steep decline in national income as prices for basics climbed.

The Nuclear Deal

In 2015, Iran agreed to curb its nuclear program in exchange for relief from the sanctions. The resulting agreement was called the JCPOA (Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action), was signed by Iran and six world powers.

Under the deal, Iran reduced its nuclear activities and allowed international inspections. In return, as sanctions were erased, the economy showed signs of

recovery, ramped up oil exports and many Iranians felt a renewed sense of optimism. It was short-lived as President Trump withdrew the US from JCPOA, saying that it was not strict enough and reimposed the sanctions in 2018.

Iran's economy suffered again. Inflation rose. The value of the Iranian currency fell.

How the US Benefits

The answer is both yes and no.

On one hand, the US not only tries to stop Iran from becoming powerful in the Middle East but also wants to protect its allies like Israel and Saudi Arabia. Sanctions were designed to pressure Iran into conforming to US expectations.

However, on the other side of the coin, these sanctions also cost US companies. US businesses are not allowed to trade with Iran and so they miss out on the potential of a large market.

Industries such as agriculture, aerospace, and technology suffer as they are unable to sell their products in Iran, resulting in lost opportunities and revenue.

Impact on Global Economy

Iran is far from a small player. When it is unable to sell oil due to sanctions, this directly impacts global oil prices, causing a rise. This ripple effect is felt worldwide. Higher oil prices make transportation and

food more expensive everywhere.

Additionally, nations like China, India and Russia don't always align with US sanctions.

This creates tension between the major world powers, affecting global trade routes, banking systems and even food supplies.

Effects on Iranian People

Beyond headlines are the lives of ordinary Iranians people who like anyone else go to school and go to work and dream of a better future.

But sanctions have made everyday life overwhelmingly difficult. Hospitals struggle to get enough medicine as well as some food and basic items are too expensive.

Unemployment remains high. Highly educated young Iranians find themselves without job opportunities.

Internet restrictions and rising costs make daily life difficult.

At the end it is not just governments that clash, it's ordinary people who bear the brunt.

“The US not only tries to stop Iran from becoming powerful in the Middle East but also wants to protect its allies like Israel and Saudi Arabia.”

Youth and Education Suffer

Sanctions don't just affect money and oil. They also affect dreams. Iranian students who want to study abroad often can't get visas or funding. Foreign universities reportedly avoid them due to US rules. As a result, international cooperation with Iran in the education sector's science and research is blocked.

The Hidden War on Science

There is another dark side that most people do not talk about. Over the last 70 years Israel and the US have reportedly killed around 2,800 Muslim scientists.

This shocking number was even published by The Times of Israel. If true this shows a deliberate effort to stop scientific progress in Muslim countries.

In 2020, Iran's top nuclear physicist Mohsen Fakhrizadeh was assassinated. He was a senior officer in the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps and a renowned professor of physics. Fakhrizadeh led many of Iran's scientific research programs and was considered the driving force behind several national defense and innovation projects.

In 2007, the United Nations Security Council did identify Fakhrizadeh as a key figure in Iran's nuclear program. After his death the then US President Donald Trump shared the news and praised Israel's Mossad intelligence agency for carrying out the killing. This was not just a loss for Iran. It was a loss for science and peace.

Can There Be a Solution?

Many experts argue that dialogue, not confrontation, is the key to resolving the long-standing tension between the US and Iran.

If both sides return to the negotiating table with a willingness to compromise, there's potential for real progress. A fair and sustainable deal could give Iran the breathing room it needs to rebuild its economy, while allowing the US to shift focus toward other pressing global challenges. Improved trade ties would mean more jobs, less economic

hardship and a better quality of life for ordinary people.

About the Authors:

Mahdi Hasan is an undergraduate student pursuing a degree in the Environmental & Resource Economics programme at the Dhaka School of Economics. Apart from his field of study, he also has a passion for the liberal arts and loves to marvel at the complexities of the geopolitical arena.

He can be reached at:

mahdihasanadib001@gmail.com

Md. Rashedul Hasan Siam is also pursuing a degree in Environmental and Resource Economics at the Dhaka School of Economics. Alongside his studies, he is actively involved in 360° digital marketing. He is interested in marketing, content writing, coding and continuously exploring new skills at the intersection of technology and marketing.

He can be reached at:

rhs.dsce@gmail.com

Strategic Shift: Keir Starmer's coalition for Ukraine peace amid uncertain US support

By Nahid Islam

Keir Starmer in a meeting of global leaders; Source: BBC

Under US President Donald Trump's second term, the Russia - Ukraine situation is clearly moving toward a resolution that satisfies Russia at the expense of Ukraine in exchange for peace. This tendency is in line with Trump's belief in the law of the jungle, where might makes right, so this is unsurprising in my view.

At the same time, Trump's demand for Ukraine's rare earth resources also fits the nature of American capitalists, who always ensure fair trade and never engage in unprofitable deals.

However, whether the future world will be led or brought back to an international order based on the rule that "the strong are right and the weak are out of luck" is something that Trump's global supporters should carefully consider. Three Worlds Theory, introduced in the 1970s, categorized global powers based on their hegemonic ambitions rather than ideology.

The U.S. and the Soviet Union formed the First World, developed nations like those in Europe and Australia comprised the Second World, and developing countries in Asia, Africa, and Latin America were labeled the Third World. This framework allowed China, despite its socialist ideology, to align with underdeveloped nations and position itself as their representative.

With the Cold War's end, the First World concept has largely disappeared, while the Second World is rarely referenced, often replaced by terms like "developed countries" or "the Western world." However, Third World remains widely used to describe underdeveloped nations advocating for equality, independence, and development. The question now arises: Should the Three Worlds Theory be reconsidered in today's rapidly evolving global landscape?

What concerns me most is the emerging second world in this new global order — countries that are neither underdeveloped

economies nor part of the Three Kingdoms struggle of the first world. This includes traditional Western and Northern European developed nations, former Eastern Bloc countries that broke away from the Soviet Union, and newly industrialised nations like South Korea. In my view, today's European Union and NATO members (excluding the US) essentially constitute this awkwardly positioned second world.

These countries are not economically poor, but none of them has the territorial size, natural resources, population or military strength to be a true global power. The UK has long lost its global influence and remains largely indifferent to continental European affairs.

The entire European continent has been heavily dependent on the US for security and economic stability, while its energy reliance on Russia has also been exposed. This is precisely why, despite being the party most directly threatened by Russian military actions, Europe has only acted under the urging and supervision of the US. Matters of European security can still be privately negotiated between the two dominant leaders of the US and Russia — a clear indication of Europe's secondary status in global power politics.

Seen through this new Three Worlds framework as well as the second world concept, the precarious position and tragic fate of Ukraine as a sovereign nation-state become all too apparent. I cannot help but conclude that while great powers certainly have their own tragedies, small nations — especially those caught in unfortunate geographic positions and unable to skillfully navigate complex international dynamics — face even greater tragedies.

After all, the fundamental law of the jungle, where power dictates outcomes, has never truly changed in this world. The article highlights the ongoing uncertainty about the war's outcome three years after Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, with major consequences for Ukraine, Europe, and global security. A Russian victory could embolden Moscow to challenge NATO and alter post-Soviet borders, while failure could deter future aggression and impact China's strategy on Taiwan. The potential role of former U.S. President Donald Trump in seeking a deal to end the war is explored, with questions about whether he would pursue a quick, narrow agreement or a broader deal involving European security.

The article also addresses the challenges in reaching a substantive agreement with Russia, especially given its harsh demands, and the possible involvement of European NATO troops in securing a peace deal. The likelihood of a "big deal," including the roles of Europe and China, is considered unlikely.

The credibility of NATO's Article 5 and the potential impact of Trump undermining NATO are discussed, particularly regarding European security. Europe's growing defense burden is noted, with estimates suggesting the need for increased spending beyond the current 2% of GDP. Without U.S. support, Europe would struggle to defend itself against Russian aggression, weakening NATO's effectiveness.

Despite heavy casualties, Russia has continued its military operations with recruitment incentives and mercenaries, although territorial gains have been minimal. Ukraine has inflicted significant damage on Russia but faces its own challenges, including battlefield exhaustion

and recruitment struggles. Western military aid remains crucial, but political uncertainty about continued support—especially with the upcoming U.S. elections and potential policy shifts under a Trump administration—raises concerns. Ukraine's ability to sustain its war effort will depend on continued arms supplies and loosening restrictions on using Western weapons against Russian territory. The coming months are critical in determining whether Ukraine can maintain its resistance or if Russia will exploit its vulnerabilities.

British Prime Minister Keir Starmer has proposed forming a “coalition of the willing” to create a peace plan for Ukraine and present it to U.S. President Donald Trump for his support. This move follows tensions between Trump and Ukrainian President Zelenskyy, signaling a potential shift in U.S. support for Ukraine. Starmer's coalition includes several European leaders who met at a security summit in London, where they agreed on four key points: supporting Ukraine's sovereignty, ensuring Ukraine's involvement in negotiations, continuing military aid, and boosting Ukraine's defense capabilities if a peace deal is reached. Starmer also announced a new £1.6 billion deal with Ukraine for air defense missiles.

A “coalition of the willing” refers to countries coming together temporarily to achieve a specific goal, without being part of a formal organization like the EU or NATO. The coalition's primary task is to create a peace plan that addresses Ukraine's security while being acceptable to Trump, who has indicated that the U.S. or NATO will not offer security guarantees to Ukraine.

The coalition currently includes the UK, France, and other European nations, though

the specifics are still unclear. The plan may involve a ceasefire and peacekeeping forces, with France and the UK expressing a willingness to send peacekeepers.

Starmer's initiative comes after the U.S.-Russia peace talks in Saudi Arabia excluded European and Ukrainian leaders, a gap that Starmer aims to fill. However, experts stress that the plan's success depends on continued U.S. support for Ukraine, particularly in terms of military aid, as any peace agreement without U.S. backing is unlikely to be sustainable.

While coalitions of the willing have existed before, such as in the 1999 East Timor peace mission and the 2003 Iraq invasion, the question remains whether this coalition can effectively help Ukraine without U.S. involvement. Both Starmer and Zelenskyy have acknowledged that U.S. support is crucial for the success of any peace plan.

About the Author

Nahid Islam is an undergraduate student pursuing a degree in the Environmental & Resource Economics programme at the Dhaka School of Economics.

He can be reached at:

nahidislamsohan1996@gmail.com

Geoeconomics of Sustainability

Will NCQG Survive Global Arms Race?

Raisa Shaker Nishat . From Australia

Environmental Climate Mitigation Enthusiast

Illustration: Mahdi/Econology/

In recent months, Western countries, most notably the United Kingdom, European Union, and Canada have committed to exceptional increases in defence spending in response to the volatility surrounding Russia's invasion of Ukraine, growing instability in the Indo-Pacific, and concerns about U.S. foreign policy shifts. These military budget hikes, unprecedented in scope for decades, reflect a major recalibration in the way advanced economies allocate resources.

This surge in military expenditure, particularly against the backdrop of sustained economic uncertainty, presents a profound threat to the global climate agenda. Specifically, it jeopardizes the achievement of the New Collective Quantified Goal (NCQG)—the critical

\$300 billion annual climate financing target aimed at mitigating the effects of climate change. The NCQG represents a collective pledge from developed countries to provide significant financial assistance to developing nations to combat climate change.

Yet, in an era marked by prolonged military build-ups, where national security is increasingly prioritized, climate finance risks being relegated to the background.

At the heart of the issue is the geoeconomic power shift which is happening as defence spending is increasingly taking precedence over economic policies that favour long-term sustainability. While military budgets are inherently inflexible, driven by multi-year contracts and long-term defence

procurements, climate funding is often discretionary, leaving it vulnerable to fiscal cuts. This dynamic exposes the precarious position of climate financing in the face of rising geopolitical tensions, where even well-intended environmental goals may fall victim to broader geopolitical calculations.

A Changing Military Landscape: UK, EU, and Canada at the Forefront

The UK's pledge to raise its defence budget to 2.5% of GDP by 2027, and potentially up to 3%, signals a major departure from its past defence strategy. For the better part of three decades, the UK's defence spending hovered around 2%—a level that was sufficient to meet NATO's requirements without burdening the economy. However, the Russia-Ukraine conflict has shifted the calculus, with the UK government acknowledging the need for a robust military that can meet the challenges of both traditional and emerging security threats.

This change is not merely a temporary budgetary shift; it marks a strategic recalibration. The UK has not embarked on such a drastic increase in defence spending since the Cold War era, underscoring the scale of the security concerns at hand. For a country that had historically allocated resources to welfare and climate initiatives, the decision to prioritize military defence at the expense of economic and environmental resilience is a wake-up call for global climate policy. The EU is not far behind. Nations like Germany and France, which had long embraced a low defence

budget relative to their economic weight, are now shifting focus.

The EU's "war economy mode"—a term not used in its modern history—refers to an embrace of policies that redirect public funding to military production and defence infrastructure. As a result, European climate finance commitments may take a backseat as governments re-prioritize military-industrial complexes. The EU faces an unsettling choice: continue supporting climate financing for vulnerable nations or focus on rearmament.

“European climate finance commitments may take a backseat as governments re-prioritize military-industrial complexes.”

Meanwhile, Canada's \$77 billion defence expansion further entrenches the trend of defence spending, particularly as uncertainty over U.S. security guarantees grows under shifting political leadership. While Canada has committed to climate goals, this increased military expenditure raises the question: will the climate financing envelope get thinner as U.S. policy shifts further destabilise the North American defence framework?

The U.S. Factor: A Global Climate Finance Vacuum

At the global level, the United States remains the world's largest contributor to climate financing, having pledged \$11 billion annually to climate aid under President Biden. However, this generous funding could be at risk. As Donald Trump returns to office, his administration's track record on climate finance—marked by earlier precedence of withdrawal from the Paris Agreement and a broader aversion to multilateral climate commitments—would likely result in severe cuts to U.S.

contributions, weakening the financial backbone of the NCQG. Such a retreat would create a power vacuum in global climate leadership, one that China would not hesitate to fill in. While China has increasingly positioned itself as a leader in green technology and climate diplomacy, it remains the world's largest carbon emitter and is still heavily reliant on coal-fired energy. Yet, if the U.S. retracts, China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) could pivot to become a climate financing tool for developing nations—albeit with China's own geopolitical ambitions at the core.

Russia: A Detractor to NCQG

On the other hand, Russia's interests lie directly at odds with global climate financing. Its economic model, deeply entrenched in fossil fuel exports, would be fundamentally threatened by a well-funded NCQG, which would accelerate global transitions away from fossil fuels. Russia is likely to not only oppose the NCQG in international forums but could also engage in disinformation campaigns to discredit international climate finance frameworks. In Russia's view, NCQG represents an economically self-serving initiative by the West, undermining the foundation of resource-dependent economies.

The Path Forward: Protecting Climate Finance Amid Geopolitical Rivalries

Given the intertwined nature of security and climate priorities, the challenge now is to prevent military spending from displacing climate finance. Here are a few key strategies to safeguard the NCQG:

1. **Ring-fence Climate Funding:** Establish legal frameworks that guarantee climate funding is shielded from defence

spending adjustments. Governments must recognize climate financing as a core pillar of national security.

2. **Sustainable Defense Technologies:** Military budgets should support green defence technologies, like renewable-powered military equipment, to align defence spending with environmental sustainability.

3. **Private Sector Mobilization:** Corporations and financial institutions must be incentivized to channel funds into green bonds, climate investment initiatives, and carbon markets to supplement public climate finance.

4. **Economic Integration of Climate Action:** Governments should embed climate resilience into national economic strategies so that environmental action is seen as a driver of long-term economic growth, rather than an isolated cost.

Conclusion: In the coming years, defence spending and climate finance will be locked in a zero-sum contest, where military expenditure threatens to overshadow climate commitments. The key question remains: will countries embrace the economic and environmental resilience that climate action offers, or will they prioritise the short-term demands of security, leaving climate finance vulnerable? As military budgets grow, geopolitical competition for resources could determine the fate of global climate goals.

About the Author

Raisa Shakera Nishat is an environmentalist hailing from Australia. She can be reached at:
nishat0309@gmail.com

Sustaining Bangladesh's Beauty: Tackling overtourism through ecotourism

By Md Mejba Hossan Abid & Md Aqib ur Rahman Mozumdar

Tourism has become a vital part of Bangladesh's economy, bringing in revenue, creating jobs, and fostering cultural exchange. With breathtaking landscapes like Cox's Bazar, the Sundarbans, and the hill tracts of Bandarban, the country attracts millions of visitors every year. However, the rapid and unregulated growth of tourism has led to overtourism in several locations, causing environmental harm, cultural erosion, and economic challenges for local communities. As an alternative, ecotourism has emerged as a responsible approach to travel, prioritising conservation and sustainable development.

To ensure a future where tourism benefits both the environment and people, Bangladesh must strike a careful balance between growth and sustainability. Overtourism occurs when the number of visitors to a destination exceeds its capacity, leading to significant environmental, social, and infrastructural problems. In Bangladesh, the consequences of overtourism are becoming increasingly evident.

Environmental and ecological damage

One of the most affected destinations is Cox's Bazar, home to the world's longest unbroken sea beach. While tourism has boosted the local economy, it has also brought excessive littering, plastic pollution, and light and noise disturbances

that threaten the beach's delicate ecosystem. Endangered sea turtles, which once nested along the shore, are now at risk due to human activity.

The Sundarbans, the largest mangrove forest in the world and a UNESCO World Heritage site, is another destination suffering from excessive tourism.

The increasing number of tour boats and visitors disturbs the habitat of the Royal Bengal Tiger, depletes natural resources, and contributes to pollution. Unregulated tourism, combined with illegal logging, is putting immense pressure on this fragile ecosystem.

Other natural sites, such as Saint Martin's Island, are facing similar threats. As Bangladesh's only coral island, its ecosystem is extremely fragile, yet the unregulated construction of hotels, plastic waste, and uncontrolled foot traffic are causing severe damage to marine biodiversity. Without immediate intervention, the island's coral reefs may be lost forever.

Cultural and social disruptions

Overtourism does not only affect nature—it also alters the social and cultural fabric of communities. Sajek Valley, once a quiet tribal settlement, has seen a rapid transformation into a commercialised tourist hotspot. The traditional lifestyle of indigenous communities is being overshadowed by the influx of resorts, hotels, and restaurants

that cater to mass tourism, leading to a loss of cultural heritage. In Old Dhaka, historic sites like Lalbagh Fort and Ahsan Manzil are experiencing overcrowding, which accelerates the wear and tear of these centuries-old landmarks.

Without strict conservation measures, these cultural treasures may lose their authenticity and historical value.

Even the daily lives of locals are being affected. In places like Kuakata, a rise in tourism has led to price inflation, making basic goods more expensive for residents.

Traditional fishermen and small business owners are struggling to keep up with the changing economic conditions, as larger businesses monopolise the tourism industry.

Overtourism also strains local infrastructure. Sreemangal, known for its vast tea gardens and the Lawachara National Park, is experiencing increasing foot traffic.

The influx of tourists disrupts wildlife, causes littering, and creates pressure on limited resources such as water and sanitation facilities.

Without careful management, the area's natural charm could be permanently damaged.

The same issue is evident in Saint Martin's Island, where the lack of proper waste management is worsening environmental conditions. With no effective restrictions on tourist numbers, pollution levels are rising, putting marine life in danger and damaging the very ecosystem that attracts visitors.

Embracing Ecotourism for a Sustainable Future

To counteract the negative effects of overtourism, Bangladesh is increasingly turning towards ecotourism. This form of tourism prioritises responsible travel, conservation, and community involvement, ensuring that destinations remain unspoiled for future generations.

In the Sundarbans, the government has introduced strict regulations to control visitor numbers and tour routes, minimising human interference in wildlife habitats. Ecotourism projects have also been launched, employing local communities to provide guided tours and alternative livelihoods that reduce reliance on deforestation and poaching.

Similarly, Sreemangal has embraced sustainable tourism through eco-resorts that promote low-impact travel. Many of these lodges employ local indigenous guides, ensuring that tourism benefits the community while preserving traditional knowledge. Lawachara National Park has also implemented strict visitor regulations to protect its unique biodiversity.

On Saint Martin's Island, some eco-resorts are adopting renewable energy sources and waste management practices to lessen the environmental footprint of tourism.

Although these efforts are in the early stages, they highlight the potential for sustainable tourism models in Bangladesh.

In Sajek Valley, community-led tourism initiatives encourage visitors to engage with indigenous communities, learning about their traditions rather than imposing commercial developments.

By promoting cultural tourism that respects local heritage, Bangladesh can protect its diverse ethnic identities while fostering responsible travel.

Key Strategies for Balancing Tourism Growth

Regulating Tourist Numbers – To prevent excessive footfall, Bangladesh should introduce visitor caps on sensitive destinations like Saint Martin’s Island and the Sundarbans. A model similar to Bhutan’s “high-value, low-impact” strategy could be applied, where tourists pay an environmental fee that supports conservation efforts.

Promoting Off-Peak Travel – Encouraging tourism during the monsoon or off-seasons can help distribute visitors more evenly throughout the year. Additionally, promoting lesser-known destinations such as Nafakhum Waterfall and Tetulia could reduce pressure on overburdened sites.

Investing in Eco-Friendly Infrastructure – Sustainable hotels, waste management systems, and renewable energy solutions should be prioritised. In places like Cox’s Bazar and Saint Martin’s Island, implementing effective waste disposal mechanisms is crucial to preserving the environment.

Educating Tourists – Awareness campaigns can teach travellers the importance of responsible tourism. Simple steps like reducing plastic waste, respecting local cultures, and supporting community-run businesses can make a significant difference. Tour guides should also be trained in eco-tourism principles to educate visitors on conservation efforts.

Leveraging Technology – Big data and AI can help predict and manage tourist

flows, ensuring that destinations like Cox’s Bazar do not become overcrowded. Additionally, virtual tourism—offering online experiences of historical and cultural sites—can provide alternative ways to explore Bangladesh’s heritage without causing physical strain on fragile locations.

A Shared Responsibility

The future of Bangladesh’s tourism industry depends on a collective effort from governments, businesses, and tourists. The government must enforce strict regulations, promote sustainable tourism policies, and provide incentives for eco-friendly businesses.

Businesses should invest in responsible tourism models, employ local communities, and prioritise environmental conservation. Tourists must make conscious choices—opting for eco-friendly accommodations, reducing waste, and respecting local traditions.

With more than 70% of Bangladeshi travellers expressing a preference for sustainable tourism, the demand for responsible travel is growing. The government aims to make 30% of the tourism industry sustainable by 2030, highlighting the country’s commitment to balancing tourism growth with environmental and cultural preservation.

Bangladesh stands at a crossroads—continue the path of uncontrolled mass tourism or embrace a sustainable future where ecotourism thrives. The country’s natural beauty, cultural heritage, and economic stability depend on the choices made today. By implementing thoughtful policies, investing in sustainable infrastructure, and fostering responsible

travel habits, Bangladesh can create a tourism industry that benefits both visitors and locals while protecting the nation's most precious treasures.

The challenge is clear, but so is the opportunity. Will Bangladesh rise to the occasion and set a global example for sustainable tourism? The answer lies in our collective actions.

About the Authors:

Md Mejba Hossan Abid is currently studying

Environmental and Resource Economics at the Dhaka School of Economics. He enjoys writing about economics, playing numeric game as well as travelling.

He can be reached at:

mejbahossan77@gmail.com

Md Aqib ur Rahman Mozumdar is also studying Environmental & Resource Economics at the Dhaka School of Economics. He loves diving into books and expressing his thoughts through writing.

He can be reached at:

ratul3.33.333.3333@gmail.com

Bangladesh's Economic Crossroads: Growth, challenges, path forward

By Israt Tasnim Mahisa

Bangladesh, a South Asian nation of over 170 million people, has emerged as a remarkable success story in the global economic landscape. Over the past two decades, the country has demonstrated resilience and adaptability, with consistent GDP growth, industrial expansion, and infrastructural advancements. However, as of March 2025, the nation finds itself at a crucial juncture, grappling with economic headwinds, political transformations, and social challenges that will determine its trajectory in the years ahead.

Sustained growth and emerging challenges

Bangladesh's economic growth has been impressive, averaging between 6 and 7 per cent annually over the past decade. However, recent inflationary pressures and

global trade disruptions have tempered this momentum. The World Bank estimates GDP growth at 5.2 per cent for the 2024-25 fiscal year, slightly lower than pre-pandemic levels. Several key sectors continue to drive the economy, including agriculture, manufacturing, and services.

Agriculture remains vital, contributing approximately 12 per cent to GDP and employing a large portion of the population. Meanwhile, the ready-made garment (RMG) industry, the backbone of Bangladesh's economy, accounts for over 80 per cent of exports. The service sector has also seen steady expansion, contributing around 50 per cent to GDP, with banking, telecommunications, and IT services playing significant roles. Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) have emerged as another critical pillar, generating

employment and contributing nearly 25 per cent to GDP. Government initiatives such as low-interest loans have further supported this sector, encouraging entrepreneurship and economic diversification.

Yet, challenges persist. Inflation has soared to 9.8 per cent in early 2025, driven by rising food and energy prices. The Bangladeshi Taka has also depreciated against the US dollar, making imports more expensive and exacerbating inflationary pressures. In response, the Bangladesh Bank has implemented monetary policy measures, including higher interest rates and liquidity control. However, external factors such as global oil price volatility and supply chain disruptions continue to pose significant risks.

Political transformation and structural reforms

The political landscape of Bangladesh underwent a seismic shift in August 2024 with the ousting of former Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina following widespread protests. Nobel laureate Muhammad Yunus assumed leadership of the interim government, ushering in a new era of political and economic reform. Yunus's administration has prioritised restoring democratic institutions, tackling corruption, and implementing structural changes aimed at fostering transparency and investor confidence.

Despite these reform efforts, foreign direct investment (FDI) has remained inconsistent due to policy uncertainties and bureaucratic inefficiencies. In 2024, FDI inflows stood at approximately \$2.9 billion, marking a decline from previous years. The government has since introduced incentives such as tax benefits, improved

infrastructure, and streamlined business registration processes to attract investors. Nevertheless, sustained efforts will be required to build investor confidence and ensure long-term economic stability.

The country has also made significant strides in infrastructure development, with projects such as the Padma Bridge, Dhaka Metro Rail, and deep-sea ports improving connectivity and reducing transportation costs.

These initiatives are expected to enhance trade and boost industrial growth. Simultaneously, Bangladesh's digital transformation is gathering pace, with the ICT sector expanding at an annual rate of 8-10 per cent. The "Digital Bangladesh" initiative has facilitated financial inclusion, e-commerce, and digital services, contributing to economic modernisation. The government's ambitious "Smart Bangladesh 2041" programme aims to further integrate artificial intelligence, blockchain technology, and automation into the national economy.

Social and Environmental Challenges

Despite economic progress, social challenges persist, particularly in youth unemployment and income inequality. The youth unemployment rate stands at around 10.2 per cent, reflecting a mismatch between skills and job market demands.

Rural-urban disparities also remain stark, with rural populations facing limited access to healthcare, education, and financial services. To address these issues, the government has prioritised inclusive policies, expanding vocational training programmes and promoting entrepreneurship among the youth.

Bangladesh is also on the frontline of climate change, experiencing rising sea levels, floods, and cyclones that threaten livelihoods and economic stability. The government has ramped up its climate resilience efforts, investing in renewable energy, disaster management, and sustainable agriculture. Solar and wind power initiatives are expanding rapidly, with a target to generate at least 30 per cent of the country's electricity from renewable sources by 2030. These efforts aim to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and mitigate environmental risks.

Another pressing issue is the Rohingya refugee crisis, which continues to strain Bangladesh's economy and resources. The country hosts a substantial refugee population, and recent funding shortfalls have led to concerns over food shortages and humanitarian aid. UN Secretary-General António Guterres has urged increased international support to prevent

a worsening crisis.

Looking ahead, Bangladesh's economic future hinges on its ability to navigate these complex challenges while sustaining growth. Key policy recommendations include diversifying exports beyond RMG, enhancing FDI inflows through regulatory reforms, investing in human capital, expanding sustainable infrastructure, and strengthening governance. If managed effectively, these measures will position Bangladesh as a resilient and dynamic economy, paving the way for its transition to an upper-middle-income country in the coming years.

About the author

Israt Tasnim Mahisa is currently studying Environmental and Resource Economics at the Dhaka School of Economic. She loves exploring new ideas and making a positive impact. She can be reached at: isratmahisa41@gmail.com

A Nation in Fear: Devastating toll of sexual violence in Bangladesh

By Joysa Saha, Priyanjana Pal Preety

Sexual violence in Bangladesh is not just a statistic—it is a harrowing reality that has left thousands of women and children traumatised, their lives forever altered. Beyond the numbers lie stories of shattered dreams, lost dignity, and a pervasive fear that grips communities. Despite years of advocacy and activism, the justice system remains slow, societal stigma persists, and survivors often find themselves fighting

alone against a system that fails them.

A Crisis Deep-Rooted in Society

Between 2019 and 2024, under the leadership of Sheikh Hasina, reports of rape and abuse reached alarming levels. More than 43,000 women—including 7,000 children—became victims of rape in just six years, according to media reports. Some were attacked due to political

affiliations, others simply for being women in a society where power is often wielded as a tool of intimidation and violence. When university students and activists protested, many were met with sexual assault at the hands of government forces and ruling-party activists.

For every reported case, there are countless others that remain unspoken, buried beneath shame, societal pressure, and a broken legal system. Survivors often refrain from seeking justice, knowing that they will face blame rather than support. Even those who step forward endure drawn-out trials, invasive questioning, and the pain of seeing their attackers walk free due to corruption and political interference.

Some of the most heinous cases in recent years include the 2024 Jahangirnagar University rape case, where a woman was attacked in what should have been a safe academic environment; the 2020 MC College gang rape, where ruling-party activists brutally assaulted a woman in a college hostel; and the 2018 Subarnachar election-night rape, a case of political retribution. While some perpetrators were eventually sentenced, these instances remain the exception rather than the rule.

The Hidden Economic Consequences

Sexual violence extends beyond personal trauma; it has profound economic repercussions. Survivors often struggle with post-traumatic stress disorder, depression, and anxiety, leading many to leave their jobs or drop out of school. When women fear going to work or children hesitate to attend school, the entire nation suffers. Lost productivity, lower household incomes, and stunted human capital development slow economic progress.

The financial burden on families is immense. Hospital bills, therapy costs, and rehabilitation services add to the suffering of survivors, many of whom already struggle to make ends meet. Furthermore, Bangladesh's potential for tourism and foreign investment is hindered by its high crime rates, particularly against women. Safety concerns deter investors and tourists, resulting in fewer job opportunities and economic stagnation.

The government allocates significant resources to law enforcement, legal trials, and victim support programmes. However, without efficient enforcement and timely justice, much of this investment is wasted. Swift and effective judicial processes could redirect these funds towards national development rather than continuously fighting the same battle.

A New Government, A New Hope?

Since August 2024, Bangladesh has been under an interim government led by Dr Muhammad Yunus. While his administration has pledged to combat gender-based violence, the crisis persists. In March 2025, the brutal assault and subsequent death of an eight-year-old girl in Magura sparked nationwide outrage. Protests erupted across the country, demanding justice and safety for women and children. In response, the government made swift arrests and proposed amendments to the Women and Children Repression Prevention Act, aiming to expedite trials and ensure stricter penalties. However, legislative changes alone will not eradicate the problem. A cultural shift is necessary—one that prioritises education, awareness, and systemic reform. Comprehensive sex education, gender sensitivity training, and community-

led initiatives must be implemented to dismantle deep-rooted misogyny. Law enforcement agencies require training to handle cases with sensitivity, ensuring that survivors receive justice without further trauma. Safe shelters, crisis centres, and mental health support networks must be expanded, offering survivors a chance to heal and rebuild their lives.

Bangladesh stands at a crossroads. It can continue down a path where women live in constant fear, or it can commit to building a future where justice is swift, safety is guaranteed, and dignity is upheld. The fight against sexual violence is not just about legal reforms; it is about reclaiming the soul of a nation that has long ignored the suffering of its women and children. Real change demands collective action—because until every survivor's voice is heard, the crisis

will remain beyond numbers.

About the Authors:

Joysa Saha is currently pursuing a Bachelor's degree in Entrepreneurial Economics at the Dhaka School of Economics. She enjoys travelling and has a passion for writing.

She can be reached at:

joysasaha0@gmail.com

Priyanjana Pal Preety. is currently pursuing a degree in Environmental & Resource Economics at the Dhaka School of Economics. She has a passion for writing, traveling and discovering new experiences.

She can be reached at:

Priyanjanapreety116@gmail.com

Neglected helpful Creature

By Rafika Akter Mim

Crows are omnivorous animals, and they are much smarter than other birds. They play an important role in the environment, but they are not widely accepted socially as birds. However, they can adapt to all types of environments.

Crows belong to the Corvidae family. There are 42 species of crows in the world, and their population exceeds 1 billion. They first appeared in Australia around 17 million years ago and later spread globally. Crows are found in almost every country, except Antarctica. They are usually black, but in America, blue crows can be seen, and white crows are found in Africa. In

Bangladesh, apart from zoos, it is rare to see crows of different colors. The house crow, which is black, is most commonly seen in cities and villages. In the mountains, mountain crows can be seen in a few areas. Crows can live up to 20 years if conditions are good, but in the wild, they usually live 7-8 years. Some crows in captivity have been known to live up to 30 years.

Crows use their intelligence and different techniques to gather food. They are social as well as predatory animals. They eat fruits, insects, and dead animals, and sometimes even small living birds. Crows can remember human faces and use tools

to solve problems. They prefer to move in groups. Though their cawing might seem repetitive, they actually use over 250 different sounds to communicate. They have different calls for danger, soft calls, and food discovery. They also use body language to communicate. Just like human languages vary across regions, the crow's language can differ from country to country. Crows are extremely beneficial to the environment. They help maintain the balance of the ecosystem by spreading seeds and helping trees grow. They play an important role in keeping the environment clean by eating waste and dead bodies. They also help farmers by eating pests.

However, crows sometimes eat the eggs of smaller birds, which can harm their population. Their constant cawing also causes noise pollution, which makes city dwellers uncomfortable.

There are some superstitions about crows. Since they are often seen around dead bodies and eat carrion, they are considered symbols of misfortune in some cultures. However, in Japan, crows are seen as messengers of the gods. According to a Greek myth, crows were once white, but Apollo turned them black for lying. Most of us have grown up reading the story of "The Crow and the Pitcher." Crows are also featured in Panchatantra stories.

Research shows that the crow population in Bangladesh is increasing steadily. Around 20,000-30,000 crows live in every 100 square kilometers. However, eagles, hawks, and wild cats pose a threat to crows. Other dangers include poisoned food, getting stuck in electric wires, and loss of habitat. Another well-known and surprising characteristic of crows is that they eat cuckoo eggs and lay their own eggs in the cuckoo's nest.

Scientifically speaking, crows play an invaluable role in maintaining environmental balance. Their simple lifestyle, ability to adapt, and their conservation need show that humans must adopt a tolerant attitude towards them.

About the Author

Rafika Akter Mim is a student at the Dhaka School of Economics. She is studying Environmental and Resource Economics. She wants to work for the environment and is especially interested in the small and beautiful details of nature. Rafika dreams of building a greener and cleaner world for the future.

She can be reached at:
rafikaaktermim1902@gmail.com

Ocean Rescue 2.0: The nano battle against micro plastic pollution

Sumaiya Hassan . Research Assistant & Lab-in-charge
BioNanotechnology & Nanomedicine Lab, Islamic University

Scientist Leo Baekeland invented plastics intending to make daily life easier. Fast forward to a century: this so-called easy life accessory is now silently backstabbing us with microplastic pollution.

Our oceans are drowning in an estimated 358 trillion microplastic particles, an invisible tide of pollution suffocating marine life. If you see a floating plastic bag you can pick it up and throw it away easily but microplastics which are the byproducts of industrial waste, synthetic clothing, and degraded plastic debris with less than 5mm in length are nearly impossible to remove as they are almost invisible to naked eyes and refuse to break down easily.

This characteristic, along with their easily transportable nature and our mass consumption of plastic, has made them available from the top of the mountain to

the bottom of the sea, even in the bodies of humans and animals. The biggest sufferers in this category are marine life, as they are living and unknowingly filling their stomachs with this microscopic poison, leading to the disruption in their health, the decline of their population, and causing a permanent scar through the entire food chain, threatening biodiversity and ecosystem balance.

Scientists have tried and tested several solutions to battle this catastrophe, but the question remains: How do we fight an enemy too small to see yet too vast to ignore before it's too late?

There's an old saying: "Go back to nature if modernization doesn't have the solution", and scientists tried to couple nature and modern technology in harmony and gave us the answer for this catastrophe:

Nanocellulose-based materials. This unique hydrophilic (strong affinity for water) material is simply prepared from the fibers collected from natural sources like plants or agricultural waste and processed into nanoscale forms. But this apparently simple formulation has a game-changing capability, which is trapping microplastics.

Usually, microplastic particles have electric charges, which are like tiny magnets. Scientists found that nanocellulose fibers can attract and stick to these charged microplastics, helping to trap them and stop them from spreading in the ocean. Unlike synthetic materials used in water filtration, nanocellulose is completely biodegradable, meaning it will break down naturally without harming marine life.

This makes it a more sustainable alternative to synthetic absorbents, which may contribute to secondary pollution. China has pioneered bringing this method/concept from the lab to real-world implementation.

Researchers from Wuhan University have engineered a biodegradable sponge by merging two unexpected duos: chitin extracted from squid bones and cotton cellulose. This revolutionary sponge has been proven to remove up to 99.8% of microplastics from various water sources, including lakes, seawater, irrigation systems, and ponds.

Another major success for this team was that they were able to prioritize affordability and sustainability by using natural resources while not compromising the effectiveness, which is the recipe for being a strong candidate for large-scale production. Hence, they are already looking ahead, with plans to expand production

and integrate this sponge into major water treatment facilities and even household water filters. Now the question is what it have to do with Bangladesh? Bangladesh is a heavily water body-dependent country. Pollution in water means a direct threat to both the county's public health and one of the bases of the economy: agriculture.

Hence, the cleaner the rivers and coastal water are, the better our economy and livelihood. But, as a developing country, is adopting this technology realistic or a mere fairytale for us? The answer is yes, and we are ahead with a trump card which is the production of a load of cellulose-based or plant-based agricultural waste- a prime ingredient for nanocellulose formation that could be recycled and used for this method.

However, investing in research, local production, and policy integration is also essential for making this venture successful in Bangladesh. The good news- the government of Bangladesh has already stepped up and initiated investments in this sector to find a solution before it's too late.

Leading universities like BUET, SUST, BAU, IU, and so on have launched several research initiatives to find nano-scale solutions for this problem while prioritising sustainability. Some of them are on their way to publishing their work soon and authorising the technology or instrument. If it becomes successful, "Microplastic Poisoning" may soon become a thing of the past. So the Nano-warriors are coming to the rescue, but are we ready to deploy them?

About the Author

Sumaiya Hassan is currently a Research Assistant at Islamic lab, She can be reached at Email: sumaiyahassan80@gmail.com

